

Real-time Joint Based Human Activity Recognition using RGB-Depth Camera

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Abstract—Human activity recognition (HAR) has gained an effective role for computer vision in the problem of video surveillance systems and medical purposes. This study represents an approach for a biometric system that can recognize human activities in 3D space. Related approaches have shown that monitoring of various physiological signals can provide distinctive information to recognize human activities. The proposed method conducts a machine learning to determine a pattern on numerous activities using angles between joints in 3D space. Basically, activity related joint angles are obtained using Microsoft Kinect v2 sensor. Since HAR is operated in a time domain, joints' angle information is stored in every 20 frames. Stored information consist the feature set for human activity recognition. Support vector machine (SVM) is used for both train and test. Among six different human activities, obtained average accuracy is 99,999482 %.

Keywords—Human activity recognition; Machine Learning; Support Vector Machine; Microsoft Kinect v2; RGB-Depth camera

I. INTRODUCTION

Human activity recognition (HAR) intends to recognize human activities using adopting model. It is quite useful to various human centered life problems such as video surveillance systems, medical systems and eldercares. Activity recognition can be completed successfully, for instance, by utilizing the information captured from sensors such as accelerometers [1]. These sensors could already be embedded in some smartphones. So, it is possible to benefit from these sensors to make a classification on human activities such as standing, walking, laying, walking upstairs and walking downstairs etc. [2]. It can also be accomplished by using RGB and RGB-depth cameras by means of body parts' signals though a supervised machine learning algorithms.

Human activity understanding includes activity recognition and activity pattern discovery. Human activity recognition (HAR) aims to detect human activities with high accuracy by adopting a predefined activity model. To do so, human activity recognition, first a high-level conceptual model needs to be built, and then run the model by creating a suitably pervasive system. Meanwhile, activity pattern discovery is more related to finding unknown patterns directly coming from low-level sensor data without any predefined models or assumptions. Therefore, a pervasive system needs to be built first before analyzing the sensor data to discover activity patterns. Despite the difference in approach of each technique, their goal is the same as improving human activity technology [3].

In this study, we made a biometric system which uses angles between skeletal joints to make human activity recognition in 3D space using Microsoft Kinect v2 sensor. After angles are obtained, they are stored in a queue temporarily and used as a feature set. By means of Support Vector Machine algorithm, the patterns of the activity are decoded. In testing process, the system checks the human activity pattern for every 20 frames and decides which action it is.

This paper is organized as following way: In section 2, utilization of RGB-Depth camera in the problem of human activity recognition and previous approaches on human activity recognition are thoroughly explained. In section 3, Support Vector Machine (SVM) is summarized as a classifier that being used in recognition of human activity. In section 4, the proposed method for human activity recognition with the description of dataset, experimental environment, and real-time performance results are specified. In the last section, conclusion and considerations about the proposed method is discussed.

II. BACKGROUND

A. Microsoft Kinect v2 on Human Activity Recognition

Since the proposed method uses angles between joints, it is quite necessary to get skeletal information. So, Microsoft Kinect v2 provides a great ease to get skeletal data using its own software development kit. Microsoft Kinect v2 sensor is able to detect 25 different skeletal joints, and it can be seen in Fig. 1. Kinect can not only recognize a people, but also track them. Using infrared (IR) sensor, it is possible to detect up to six people in the scene, however only two of them can be tracked.

The range of the sensor can be determined by the setting of IR sensor. In default settings, it can recognize a person standing between 0.8 meters and 4.0 meters away, however Microsoft's suggestion is between 1.2 to 3.5 meters.

After obtaining skeletal data, angles can be obtained by applying mathematical equations. Joint angles make periodic swings in time domain. These swings makes human activity recognition possible as each activity has different swing.

Fig. 1. Microsoft Kinect v2 skeleton joint map in the scene.

B. Previous Approaches on Human Activity Recognition

Up to now, numerous approaches published on the analysis of human activity recognition. In the first instance, Gaglio, Lo Re and Morana [3] conducted Human Activity Recognition process using 3-D posture data. They implemented three different algorithms such as Hidden Markov Model and K-means clustering and Support Vector Machines. Their performance results as precision/recall is 77.3% and 76.7.

There is also another approach that proposed by Anguita, Ghio, Oneto, Parra and Reyes-Ortiz [2]. They presented a system which uses smartphone inertial sensors. To save the energy and keep the computational cost low, they used hardware friendly support vector machine. Similarly, Brown, Deitch and O'Connor [4] used smartphone data to make human activity recognition. However, their approach is different. They divided their data into two; raw data, preprocessed version of raw data. Then they presented various classifiers to analyze their effectiveness. The classifiers are Naive Bayes and Gaussian Discriminant

Analysis (GDA) on preprocessed data. Then Hidden Markov Model is conducted on GDA classifier to capture time-based relevance in the data.

Sung, Ponce, and Saxena [5] came up with the idea that uses hierarchical maximum entropy Markov Model (MEMM). First, they get the skeletal information from RGBD camera (Microsoft Kinect) and consider the human activity as composed of a set of sub-activities. Their method is tested on twelve different human activities, and achieved average accuracy is 84.3%.

III. SUPPORT VECTOR MACHINE

A Support Vector Machine (SVM) is a machine learning algorithm which learns by instance to appoint labels to objects [6]. SVM offers a statistical learning theory that declines the structural risk training error which eventually expresses an upper bound for the general minimization error [7].

A penalty term for misclassification determining a tradeoff between resolution and generalization performance [7,8] is the only parameter that needs to be set. The aforementioned algorithm continuously looks into a unique decision surface in order to support cluster vectors, and defines classification output relative to fractional data points added for support vectors with inputs obtained from samples extracted from training data. In other words, SVM classifies a pattern vector X into class $y \in \{-1,1\}$ on the basis of the support vectors X_m and corresponding classes Y_m as:

$$y = \text{sign}(\sum_{m=1}^M \alpha_m y_m K(X^m, X) - b) \quad (1)$$

where $K(.,.)$ is a symmetric absolute positive kernel function that is randomly chosen within gentle constraints. The parameters α_m and b are determined by a linearly constrained quadratic programming (QP) problem that is performed with a sequence of smaller scale, sub-problem optimizations, or an incremental scheme that controls the solution one training point at a time [7]. In a conceptual point of view, most of the training data X_m have zero coefficients α_m whereas the non-zero are returned by the constrained QP optimization that constructs the support vectors set [7,9]. The proposed system presumes that the set of support vectors and coefficients α_m are normalized Gaussian that facilitates obtaining the actual experimental performance where the efficient run-time implementation of the classifier is targeted to be obtained.

IV. PROPOSED HUMAN ACTIVITY RECOGNITION

A. System Description

The method employed in this study estimates joint angles' sequences information to recognize human activity by codifying into Support Vector Machine classifier. Compared with the other methods, suggested method uses lower cost calculations because of robust, and effective feature set. A skeletal representation of a person consists of 25 joints and angle representation is offered by Microsoft Kinect framework, namely Vitruvius. Features are selected in accordance with the relevance of the human activities. As

RGB-depth sensor is employed, the angle becomes scale and rotation invariant. It is because skeletal joint information is detected and tracked by depth sensor. Thus, location or direction of the person in the scene cannot have an effect on the performance result of the proposed study. More detailed information regarding the structure of proposed approach is suggested in Fig.2.

First of all, when the person appears in front of sensor, it is required to project the skeleton on top of the body in 2D color image. This is necessary for skeleton detection and tracking. Particularly, since Kinect combine a few sensors into one device such as RGB color camera (1920×1080), a depth sensor (512×424) and an infrared sensor (512×424), the resolutions are different and not perfectly aligned. Consequently, their view areas will be different.

Fig. 2. Block diagram for proposed real-time human activity recognition.

Projection of human body joints on RGB image requires depth sensor, the reason is that Kinect uses dept sensor for body tracking. However, in 3D space, the coordinates (x,y,z) of the human body will not be aligned in the 2D color image. So, the skeleton will be totally out of place. Since Microsoft is aware of the situation, software development kit has a proper utility named CoordinateMapper. It basically projects the points in 3D space where they correspond in 2D color image.

As mentioned in Section 2, Kinect can detect up to six people by using the infared (IR) camera. Two out of those six people can be tracked in detail. Kinect v2 sensor detects and tracks up to 25 skeletal joints, whereas Kinect v1 sensor detects up to 20 skeletal joints.

Selecting feature set for identification is the most essential part. Since the selected activities are walking, standing, jumping, lifting, sitting, and handclapping, it is required to select angles between activity-relevant joints. As a result, angles of both shoulders, elbows and knees are chosen as discriminative features. Angle between two different joints j_1 and j_2 can be obtained by calculating these two joints' location in accordance with a reference point λ in 3D space. The formula to calculate angles between two different points is shown as:

$$\varphi_{j_1, j_2} = \cos^{-1} \frac{j_1 \lambda \cdot \lambda j_2}{\|j_1 \lambda\| \|\lambda j_2\|} \quad (2)$$

In this equation, $j_1 \lambda$ shows the distance between j_1 and λ in 3D space. Likewise, λj_2 represents the distance between j_2 and λ in 3D space. And the dot between these vectors

represents the dot product. In the end, $\|j_1 \lambda\|$ and $\|\lambda j_2\|$ represents the length of these vectors respectively. In this study, reference points are necessarily assigned in the middle joint among those three joints. In other words, when the right elbow is required, j_1 and j_2 will be left shoulder and left hand respectively. This method enables us to get every person's angle sequence for activity recognition.

After obtaining angle, next step is storing those angle sequences temporarily in a queue. In this case, the number of features obtained in each frame is $6 \times n$ where n represents the queue capacity. Queue capacity is assigned to 20, which creates 120 number of features for each frame. This is a concept that works as first-in, first-out object collection. For instance, it can be thought as a bridge, and the data would be cars. First car which appears in the entrance of bridge would leave the bridge first. Likely, features are enqueued in the first frame and will be dequeued in the 21st frame. At each frame, multi-label SVM classifier will classify the feature vector that is stored in queue data structure. For instance, if the queue capacity is set to 20, then; starting from the 21st frame, it will make a decision on human activity with respect to the given 120 number of features. Basic flowchart of queue concept can be seen in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Working concept of queue object collection. First data in, leaves first.

In this study, Multi-label SVM algorithm with Gaussian kernel is used to make human activity recognition. In multi-label classification, a set of target labels is appointed to each instance. In other words, it can be assumed as attributes of data-point that are not mutually unshared. Basically, in this method, it returns only one output whether or not the data belong to assigned class. For this reason, the threshold value is applied to get the expected label. In this case, the threshold value is 85% probability. If the assigned value doesn't pass the threshold, the system will return a label called 'unknown activity'. Also, in Multi-label SVM algorithm, Gaussian kernel is conducted. The reason is that some activities might draw non-linear models. So, using non-linear kernels could bring better accuracy. However, using parabolic kernel, cubic kernel etc. don't fit the nature of human activity. Therefore, Gaussian kernel is conducted.

B. Experimental Environment

In this chapter, experimental results of this study will be demonstrated. All the videos are recorded by Kyungsoong University, Department of Electronic Engineering and taken in Kyungsoong University campus, Busan, Republic of Korea. For implementation Microsoft Kinect SDK 2.0, Vitruvius, Microsoft Visual Studio 2013 are used. The Microsoft Kinect v2 sensor is placed 1.7 meters above from the ground, and user stands right in front of camera with 0 degree. 5 different people's joint angle sequences are obtained separately. Each take lasted for approximately 10 seconds for each activity. The reason is that longer takes per each person

can provide bigger amount of instances. The captured activity sequences consist of 900 to 1220 frames. Duration of each take is different for each video, because speed of activity can vary for each user. For each activity, each user is recorded 10 times. A demonstration of test performance can be seen in Fig. 4.

In the system, joint angle values of the 1st person in the scene are shown on the top of the application window that can be seen in Fig. 4. Also, in the same window, there are four different buttons that can train the system, test the system, validate the performance, and show the angles of all people, if there is more than one person.

Moreover, on the screen, there are start and stop buttons. These are used to start and stop whichever the process is, such as training, testing, and validating. In other words, it is kind of a switch for the whole system. According to the test results, the proposed approach has 99,999482 % accuracy for six different human activities which is shown Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Test results of 6 different human activities that were trained. Walking; on the left top, jumping; on the right top, sitting; on the middle left, lifting; on the middle right, handclapping: on the bottom left, standing; on the bottom right.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a new method is proposed for human activity recognition using RGB-Depth camera. Biometric features are always useful to make activity recognition. In this day and time, video surveillance systems needs new approaches to prevent crimes and provide better opportunities to medical services. The proposed method has been invented as one of the contribution to the humanity. To make unique activity recognition, the features needed to be robust, differential and easy to calculate. By this means, authors have struck upon an idea that uses angles between joints. Main impulsion was that using biometry could be scale and rotation-invariant, therefore, wherever the person locates in the video, the proposed method can conduct the recognition without any data loss. In order to do that, Multi-label Support Vector Machine algorithm with Gaussian kernel is used as a classifier with the support of queue concept. Since we are working in time domain for activity recognition, queue is quite useful to track the data in time

domain. After that, performance result is reviewed by statistical calculations and it is quite good. According to the performance results, Support Vector Machine has 99,999482 % accuracy for six different human activities. By this mean, expanding feature set would be more helpful to increase the accuracy. For instance, using relative joint distance proportion could be one of additional feature set. Thus, new feature set would not only be scale invariant, but also could be rotation invariant. Since Microsoft Kinect v2 uses depth sensor rotation will not affect the proportion of related joint distance. Detailed information about the study will be explained in the journal version of the proposed approach.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Allen, F.R., Ambikairajah, E., Lovell, N.H., Celler, B.G.: "Classification of a known sequence of motions and postures from accelerometry data using adapted gaussian mixture models. *Physiological Measurement*", 27 (10), (2006), 935.
- [2] Anguita D., Ghio A., Oneto L., Parra X., Reyes-Ortiz J.L. (2012) "Human Activity Recognition on Smartphones Using a Multiclass Hardware-Friendly Support Vector Machine". In: Bravo J., Hervás R., Rodríguez M. (eds) Ambient Assisted Living and Home Care. IWAAL 2012, Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol 7657. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
- [3] Gaglio, Salvatore et al. "Human Activity Recognition Process Using 3-D Posture Data." *IEEE Trans. Human-Machine Systems* 45 (2015): 586-597.
- [4] Brown, Matt, Trey Deitch and Lucas O'Connor, "Activity Classification with Smartphone Data.", Stanford CS 229, Fall 2013.
- [5] Jaeyong Sung, Colin Ponce, Bart Selman, and Ashutosh Saxena. "Human activity detection from RGBD images". In Proceedings of the 16th AAAI Conference on Plan, Activity, and Intent Recognition (AAAIWS'11-16). AAAI Press 47-55. 2011.
- [6] Cortes, C.; Vapnik, V., "Support-vector networks", *Machine Learning*, 20 (3): 273-29 (1995).
- [7] Genov, R., Gert, C.: Kerneltron: Support Vector "Machine" in Silicon. *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks* 14(5) (2003).
- [8] Girosi, F., Jones, M., Poggio, T., "Regularization Theory And Neural Networks Architectures", *Neural Comput.* 7, 219-269 (1995).
- [9] Vapnik, V., "The Nature of Statistical Learning Theory", Springer, New York (1995).